

Sample Name: PET Virgin 1-5 μm
Material: Polyethylene terephthalate
Size: 1-5 μm
Production Partner: TNO
Storage Conditions: Refrigerated

Summary

Physical Characteristics

- Median diameter (D_{50_v}) = 4,39 μm
- Particles have an irregular morphology
- $2,6 \times 10^{11}$ particles per gram
- 13639 cm^2/g surface area

Chemical Characteristics

- >99% $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{O}_4$ (PET) determined by XRF
- No changes due to milling observed in FTIR spectrum
- Not able to obtain a cathodoluminescence spectrum

Description of terms

- $D[4,3]$: Volume mean (μm)
- $D[3,2]$: Surface area mean (μm)
- $D[2,1]$: Spherical particle mean (μm)
- $D[1,0]$: Number length mean (μm)
- D_{50_v} : Median diameter (volume basis, μm)
- D_{50_N} : Median diameter (number basis, μm)
- N_w : Number of particles per gram plastic ($\#/g$)
- A_w : Surface area of particles per gram plastic (cm^2/g)

Particle Size Distribution (using Static Light Scattering (SLS) provided by TNO)

D[4,3]	D[3,2]	D[2,1]	D[1,0]	D50 _N	D50 _V	N _w	A _w
5,46	3,19	1,69	0,98	0,74	4,39	$2,6 \times 10^{11}$	13639

Chemical Composition (using XRF provided by Malvern Panalytical)

Chemical formula	Concentration (%)
$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{O}_4$	99,937
Element	Concentration (ppm)
Si	210
Cl	225
Ti	5
Cr	21
Mn	1
Fe	80
Ni	22
Cu	3
Zn	8
Zr	1
Pb	20

Chemical Bonding (Using μ -FTIR provided by TNO)Cathodoluminescence Spectroscopy (provided by TNO)

Not available